

Klub Golf Bogor Raya Improvement Plans Based on the Servicescape's Perception of the Customers

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ABSTRACT: Klub Golf Bogor Raya has not conducted revitalization of the field for twenty-seven years, while experts recommended golf fields be revitalized every once in twenty years (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023). As for the game, most activities in the game are crucial and placed in the Green area, therefore the Green Area would be the focal concern in this final project study. Klub Golf Bogor Raya's goal is to reach 60,000 NOP in 2023. To do this, the author conducted a customer satisfaction study of the golf field based on the Servicescape theory, especially the Green area would be a reference for Klub Golf Bogor Raya to execute decisions to reach the NOP target.

However the issue of the research method, needs to be validated, therefore the author conducted data triangulation. The study is triangulated with two sets of data: Klub Golf Bogor Raya's customer satisfaction survey, and experts' interview. All to address the assumptions that the Servicescape of Klub Golf Bogor Raya's Green area is relevant to customer satisfaction.

KEYWORDS: Customer satisfaction, Green area, servicescape, golf, hospitality.

INTRODUCTION

Klub Golf Bogor Raya is a renowned golf field in Bogor. Despite its good performance after the COVID-19 pandemic, its field has not been revitalized for twenty-seven years, while golf fields are usually revitalized once every twenty years. The author intended to conduct a study about customer satisfaction in the field.

In today's highly competitive business landscape, customer satisfaction has emerged as a critical factor for the success and longevity of organizations across various industries. Customer satisfaction refers to the degree to which customers are content with their overall experience and the products or services they receive from a company. Understanding and measuring customer satisfaction has become a top priority for businesses aiming to build a loyal customer base, achieve sustainable growth, and outperform their competitors (Hasim, et.al., 2018). The problem at hand is the need to assess and understand the current state of customer satisfaction within Klub Golf Bogor Raya. Without a clear evaluation of whether customer satisfaction is declining or increasing, Klub Golf Bogor Raya is lacking the necessary insights to make informed decisions and take appropriate actions to improve the customer experience (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023). Several previous researchers have emphasized the significant impact of customer satisfaction on organizations. These studies have indicated that satisfied customers tend to engage in behaviors that benefit the organization. For instance, satisfied customers are more likely to make additional purchases (Davras & Caber, 2019; Gerdt et al., 2019) and become repeat customers (Razak & Shamsudin, 2019). Moreover, customer satisfaction fosters loyalty and trust in the organization (Hasim, et.al., 2018), leading to an increased willingness to pay higher prices or premiums (Shamsudin, et.al., 2018). Satisfied customers also play a vital role in acquiring new clients through positive recommendations to their families and friends (Shamsudin & Razali, 2015).

Klub Golf Bogor Raya an 18 holes golf course, designed by renowned international golf course architect, Graham V. Marsh, is a 72hectare masterpiece of stunning natural beauty. In his design, Marsh is known for producing some of the region's finest golf facilities, which emphasize the site's abundance of mature vegetation and natural hazards to create and refreshing golfing (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023).

A. Business Issue

The author conducted an initial interview with the general manager of Klub Golf Bogor Raya on June 2nd, 2023. The interview covered the vision and mission and also the organizational structure as elaborated in the company profile subsection. Another thing covered is the role of customer satisfaction based on the general manager's experience as a practitioner. In fact, the largest

contributors are NOP, not non-players. Therefore, the general manager agreed that customer satisfaction, especially for players is important. In addition, players are strongly involved with the Servicescape of Klub Golf Bogor Raya, especially in the Green Area where they spent most golfing activities. Therefore, the general manager thought for players or NOP, their satisfaction is strongly related to their experience in the Green Area. The general manager then thought the declined NOP could be because the Green Area is lacking certain things.

Klub Golf Bogor Raya has a 60,000 NOP target this 2023. The NOP contributed around 70% of Klub Golf Bogor Raya's revenue (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023). Lately, the NOP growth increased after the pandemic. Therefore, the issue is to keep and acquire more NOP is Klub Golf Bogor Raya's goal to reach 60,000 NOP in 2023. To do this, the author conducted a customer satisfaction study of the golf field, especially the Green area would be a reference for Klub Golf Bogor Raya to execute decisions to reach the NOP target.

Klub Golf Bogor Raya has not conducted revitalization of the field for twenty-seven years, while experts recommended golf fields be revitalized every once in twenty years (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023). As for the game, most activities in the game is crucial and placed in the Green area, therefore the Green Area would be the focal concern in this final project study.

Customer satisfaction, as elaborated in the previous sections, holds an essential role for players. The number of NOP decreased in 2022, and the general manager admitted that besides that they never conduct customer satisfaction research, the field and especially the Green area has not been revitalized for too long. The declined NOP, the general manager thought that it could be because the Green area is not satisfying, and it could have something to do with the field not being revitalized. Recommended font sizes are shown in Table 1.

B. Research Questions & Research Objectives

Research Questions: • What are the Servicescape's perceptions of customers in the Green area in Klub Golf Bogor Raya?

- What improvement should Klub Golf Bogor Raya make based on customer's perception of the Servicescape in the Green area?
- What action should Klub Golf Bogor Raya take to achieve the improvement?

Research Objectives:

- Explore the Servicescape's perceptions of customers in the field of golf courses in Klub Golf Bogor Raya, especially in the Green area.
- Design a list of improvements to optimize customer's perception on the Servicescape in the Green area.
- Design a list of recommendations or actions for Klub Golf Bogor Raya to reach the improvements needed.

C. Research Scope & Limitation

This research is limited in certain aspects as elaborated below:

- The area: the area that the author studied in the golf field is limited to the Green area.
- Duration: This research is also conducted for three months.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Problem Exploration

Based on the business issue in the previous section, the main issue is the declining NOP in 2022. The number declined even after the trend increased in 2021 because of the pandemic. Customer satisfaction, especially in the Green area in the field, holds an essential role for players. Since most parts of golf play happened in the Green area. The space surrounding each hole and flag, which is typically between 100 and 500 square meters, is known as the "green." The putting green has an incredibly smooth surface with grass that has been evenly groomed, enabling golfers to make precise strokes on it. The green's topology and form can essentially go in any direction, although for practical purposes, it is smoother than other areas of the course. Players will be tested, though, as they must adjust their putting line for tiny slopes and humps. Although you may play golf in the rain, bad weather does become a

serious problem because flooded greens will force the course to close. The green is typically made of a thin carpet of grass. That illustrates how significant the green is in relation to other areas of the field (Waddington, 2022).

In addition, the field has not been revitalized for 27 years while golf area experts recommend golf fields to revitalize every 20 years. The declined NOP is likely because Klub Golf Bogor Raya did not revitalize.

The author used the 5-Why Method to explore the business issue which elaborated below:

5-Why Method

Based on the interview conducted with the general manager of Klub Golf Bogor Raya, the gameplay is the biggest reason for the players to come. If the gameplay is not up to their standard, they would be dissatisfied and would not revisit. Servicescape-wise, the Green area especially contributed to the quality of the gameplay. The updated revitalized Green area in that sense would increase the quality of the gameplay.

In addition to the root cause, the involved stakeholders in the business issue are elaborated below:

Involved Stakeholders

As previously mentioned, the NOP is strongly related to the quality of the field, especially the Green area. The field or the Servicescape is under the Golf Course Maintenance Department. Based on the interview with the general manager of Klub Golf Bogor Raya, NOP is generated not only directed from the Golf Course Maintenance but also from how Golf Sales & Marketing utilized the Servicescape quality for their sales and marketing activities.

B. Customer Satisfaction

Customer satisfaction has historically been thought to influence long-term customer behavior. The higher client retention, good word of mouth (WOM), also known as advocacy, and eventually financial rewards to the businesses that service them are, the more delighted the consumers are (Ranaweera & Prabhu, 2003).

Customer satisfaction significantly impacts organizations, as satisfied customers tend to buy more, repeat purchases, and be loyal to the organization (Davras & Caber, 2019; Gerdt et al., 2019; Razak & Shamsudin, 2019; Hasim, Shamsudin, Ali, & Shabi, 2018). They are willing to pay more or pay in premiums for satisfaction and recommend the company's products to their family and friends (Mohd Farid et.al, 2019). Loyal customers influence others' behavior, leading to increased sales and profits (Belwal & Amireh, 2018). The social proof principle can be used to judge risk as if everyone reacts, the rest will follow (M. F. Shamsudin, Razak, et al., 2018). Overall, customer satisfaction is crucial for organizations to succeed.

In golf, customer satisfaction components depended on three components: facilities and amenities, food and beverages, and customer service (Bencito, 2014).

In facilities and amenities, parking space with securities, physical features of facilities, fully equipped and air conditional board room and convention facilities, well-maintained cafeteria, smoking and non-smoking area, sports and recreational facilities, and public toilet and locker (Bencito, 2014). In food and beverages, quality of ingredients, taste, appeal, price, variation, classic food, refreshments and drinks, and liquor (Bencito, 2014). In customer service, excellent service beyond expectation, consistency, security, employees' courtesy and friendliness, knowledge of the employees, impactful and established, well-trained employees that give prompt service, transactions' privacy, and communication ability to customers (Bencito, 2014).

C. Servicescape

"The way the physical setting is created in organizations has barely been tapped as a tangible organizational resource" (Becker 1981). In contrast to other organizational factors like pay scales, promotions, benefits, and supervisory relationships that might inspire employees, management of the physical environment is frequently seen as incidental. In a similar vein, factors that affect how customers are drawn to and/or pleased by a company's services on the consumer side are given far more consideration than the physical environment, such as pricing, advertising, extra features, and special promotions. The physical environment can help or hinder the achievement of both internal organizational goals and outward marketing goals, according to the concept discussed here.

The significance of the physical environment varies on the nature of the job and the consumer experience, as is true of every organizational or marketing component. The argument put out here is that because consumers and staff frequently interact with a company's facilities, the physical surroundings are, generally speaking, more significant in-service situations. But not all service businesses and sectors are the same (Lovelock, 1983; Schmenner, 1986), and they don't all have to deal with the same strategic challenges while creating their Servicescapes. The typology in Figure 2.7 divides service organizations into two groups based on key distinctions in how the Servicescape is managed. Similar problems with the physical space design affect businesses that share a cell in the matrix.

Typology of Service Organizations Based on Variations in Form and Usage of the Servicescape		
Types of Service Organizations Based on Who Performs Actions Within the Servicescape	Physical Complexity of the Servicescape	
	Elaborate	Lean
Self-service (customer only)	Golf Land Surf 'n Splash	ATM Ticketron Post office kiosk Movie theater Express mail dropoff
Interpersonal services (both customer and employee)	Hotels Restaurants Health clinic Hospital Bank Airline School	Dry cleaner Hot dog stand Hair salon
Remote service (employee only)	Telephone company Insurance company Utility Many professional services	Telephone mail order desk Automated voice-messaging-based services

Typology of Service Organizations Based on Variations in Form and Usage of the Servicescape

The vertical dimension has to do with whether a client, an employee, or both are operating within the Servicescape. The "selfservice" corporation, where there are little to no staff and there is a great volume of consumer activity, is one extreme. The "remote service" is at the other end of the spectrum and involves little to no consumer interaction with the Servicescape and occasionally even little personnel interaction, such as with fully automated voice-messaging systems. Figure 2.7 shows that "interpersonal services" are situated in the middle of the two extremes. Both customers and staff can be found in those organizations and are active participants in the Servicescape. Whose needs should be considered in the environment's design depends on the relative level of involvement of customers and staff. Particular attention must be paid in interpersonal servicescapes to how the physical environment affects the type and standard of social interaction between and among customers and employees.

The types of goals a company might hope to achieve through the usage of its physical environment depend on whether consumers, staff, or both are present within the Servicescape. The inventive application of physical design in self-service environments may support positioning and segmentation strategies and advance particular marketing goals, such as consumer attraction and satisfaction. On the other hand, since few customers would ever see or experience the company's physical setting, organizational objectives like staff satisfaction, motivation, and operational efficiency could be the main aims in physical setting design for remote services. Through proper Servicescape design, organizational and marketing goals for interpersonal services may be able to be targeted. Even marketing objectives like connection building may be influenced by the physical setting's layout (Crosby, Evans, and Cowles, 1990).

The Servicescape's intricacy is depicted in Figure 2.7's horizontal dimension. There are some relatively straightforward service environments with few components, few areas, and few forms. We refer to them as "lean" environments. Given that both Ticketron locations and Federal Express drop-off kiosks operate out of a single, straightforward structure, they both qualify as lean settings. In self-service or remote service scenarios, where there is no interaction between consumers and personnel, design options for lean Servicescapes are generally simple. Other Servicescapes contain a wide variety of components and forms and are extremely complex. Environments described as "elaborate" are those. A hospital is a good example because of its several levels, rooms, high-tech equipment, and extensive variety in the functions carried out inside the building. The whole spectrum of marketing and organizational objectives can theoretically be approached in such a complex setting through careful management of the Servicescape. For instance, a patient's hospital room could be planned to increase patient happiness and comfort while also boosting worker efficiency. According to Figure 2.7, organizations like hospitals that are in the elaborate interpersonal service cell are faced with the most difficult Servicescape choices.

In addition to that, Bitner (1992) came up with a rich framework for addressing what behaviors are influenced, or why, or how one would go about planning and designing an environment to achieve the objective. It is also for exploring the role of the physical environment in service organizations. The framework is elaborated below:

Framework for Understanding Environment-User Relationships in Service Organizations.

The framework proposes that both customers and staff see a range of objective environmental influences and that both groups may react intellectually, emotionally, and physiologically to the environment. These internal reactions to the environment determine how certain customers and employees behave in the Servicescape and have social interactions with one another. The model is distinctive in its breadth of synthesis (for instance, Mehrabian and Russell focus on emotional responses only), the incorporation of both customers and employees and their interactions, and its application to commercial settings, despite sharing similarities with other models (e.g., Mehrabian and Russell 1974).

In latest researches, researchers used an integrated Bitner Model illustrated in the figure below:

Integrated Servicescape Model adapted from Bitner (2000) (Mei et.al, 2020)

In the figure, the built/physical environment and social environment both contributed to responses and outcomes (Mei et.al, 2020). The model is more seamless (Mei et.al, 2020). For this final project, the physical environment is based on golf field satisfaction variables.

D. Conceptual Framework

This research’s conceptual framework is based on the previous literature review. It is elaborated below:

Conceptual Framework (Jobst, 2015)

The conceptual framework is based on Jobst’s research (2015). The research investigates the effects of perceived primary service and perceived servicescape on customer satisfaction in theatres. The influence of perceived servicescape quality on customer satisfaction is subject to moderating individual factors, such as visitors’ theatrical competence and their motivation for attending a theatre performance (Jobst, 2015). Both theatre and golf are recreational businesses. Therefore, the authors decided that to use Jobst’s conceptual framework is relevant.

This final project used customer satisfaction components and variables as elaborated in the literature review. However, between the components, according to this final project’s scope and limitations. The component is only on facilities and amenities. The variables are the ones related to the green area as well as are physical features of facilities. For ambiance, there are temperature, air quality, odor, and noise levels. Then for the function, there are layout and terrain. Then for design, there are style and décor. In the social environment, there is also the presence of other users/players as a variable.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

This final project used in-depth interviews as the data collection method. The data collection used guided and semi-structured interviews. In semi-structured interviews, the researcher is free to ask follow-up questions and explore, even though the interviewer comes prepared with a list of topics or questions (Adams, 2015).

Semi-structured interviews are very suited for several valuable tasks, particularly when more than a few of the open-ended questions require follow-up queries. Especially consider using it when we need to ask probing, open-ended questions and want to know the independent thoughts of everyone in a group; ask probing, open-ended questions on topics that the respondents might not be candid about sitting with peers in a focus group; conducting a formative program evaluation and want one-on-one interviews with key program managers, staff, and front-line service providers; uncharted territory with unknown but potential momentous issues and the interviewers need maximum latitude to spot useful leads and pursue them (Adams, 2015).

Because of that base, many hospitality services that researched their customer satisfaction used semi-structured interview. For example, Lu et.al (2015) used interviews with managers and guests of 5-Star hotels in Taiwan and qualitative analysis to understand

definitions and perceptions of luxury, service quality, and satisfaction. Another example is Polii et.al (2019) who used r took the information from 10 informants using qualitative study which is in-depth interview.

The result of the research shows that internal and external factors such as location, food quality, service quality, and price fairness have significant influences that stimulate customers to become retained when buying the food and beverages of Solaria continuously.

Data in this research were acquired from people who play golf in Jabodetabek (Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi) cities in Indonesia as the group of cities is around or is Bogor, where Klub Golf Bogor Raya located, and also have experience playing golf in Klub Golf Bogor Raya, as based from the interview with the general manager, most customers are from Jabodetabek.

As for the questions list, the questions were designed following the customer satisfaction and servicescape variables. Prior to interview sessions, respondents would be questioned if they have played golf in Klub Golf Bogor Raya before, and only respondents who have would be allowed to be interviewed.

In addition, since this final project utilizes qualitative research, for the sample size it used the recommendation from Hennink & Kaiser (2022). It stated the study assesses saturation in qualitative research to identify sample sizes for saturation, strategies used to assess saturation, and guidance we can draw from these studies.

Saturation is considered the cornerstone of rigor in determining sample sizes in qualitative research, yet there is little guidance on its operationalization outside of grounded theory. In this systematic review, Hennink & Kaiser (2022) identified studies that empirically assessed saturation in qualitative research, documented approaches to assess saturation, and identified sample sizes for saturation. They describe an array of approaches to assess saturation that demonstrate saturation can be achieved in a narrow range of interviews (9–17) or focus group discussions (4–8), particularly in studies with relatively homogenous study populations and narrowly defined objectives (Hennink & Kaiser, 2022).

B. Research Methodology

The conducted interviews will be analyzed by narrative analysis. Narrative analysis is a qualitative research method that involves studying and analyzing the stories people tell about their lives and experiences. This method focuses on the way individuals construct their stories, the language they use, and the contexts in which they are shared (Ar Rashid, 2023).

One of the strengths of narrative analysis is its ability to provide a rich and nuanced understanding of individual experiences. In an article published in the *Journal of Narrative and Life History*, sociologist Ann Phoenix notes that narrative analysis can help researchers “explore how individuals experience and make sense of their lives in ways that are personally meaningful and culturally situated” (Phoenix, 2015). By examining the narrative structure and content of texts, researchers can gain insights into the unique perspectives and experiences of individuals.

Another strength of the narrative analysis is its ability to uncover the underlying themes and assumptions that shape narrative texts. In an article published in the journal *Qualitative Inquiry*, anthropologist Ruth Behar argues that “narrative analysis allows us to read between the lines of a text, to uncover the implicit meanings and assumptions that are often hidden beneath the surface” (Behar, 2017). By examining the narrative structure and content of texts, researchers can gain insights into the underlying beliefs, values, and cultural norms that shape individual and collective experiences.

In market research, there are tasks with uncovering the motivations of consumers to develop a product that meets their needs. Of course, researcher can always rely on common sense to determine what people think. However, that’s not going to cut it when thousands of individuals answer questions about their likes and dislikes, what they plan to do in the next few weeks, and so on. This means they need to find a way of talking about the observations that make sense within the context of other things people generally care about without making the respondents think too much. This is where narratives come in – they’re stories used as part of a larger discourse or discussion to explain something or give meaning to something else. In short, they provide context and understanding (Erlach, 2020).

A narrative technique organizes data and insights to make sure that everything it’s trying to say makes sense. For example, when doing market research, the surveys will often ask people about their thoughts and feelings on a certain topic. When people can explain their responses with some narrative, they can more easily relate them to a set of experiences and memories. Narratives also

make it easier for respondents to remember key points because they give them an anchor or framework that makes sense of what they've just said. A narrative technique mainly provides better context for the information you're trying to draw out from individuals (Erlach, 2020).

In addition to in-depth interviews, the author also conducted a data source triangulation. The utilization of many data sources, such as time, place, and people, in a study, is known as data triangulation. The validity and reliability of the results can be increased by correlating the findings and making up for any data deficiencies with the strengths of other data. The method has been applied in numerous fields to enhance conclusions about findings and lower the possibility of erroneous interpretations (Hardy et.al, 2004).

Data triangulation is also called cross-examination because it double or even triple-checks the results obtained from the research. The basic idea behind this or the rationale for using this approach is that one can be more confident and can increase the credibility and validity of the findings when different methods yield the same results.

In doing so the researcher would ultimately arrive at a complete and more wholesome picture of the phenomenon or situation under investigation. This is what the proponents of data triangulation argue, is the basic purpose of using this approach that it helps in "giving a more detailed and balanced picture of the situation" (Altrichter et al. 1996)

When applied to qualitative research this method may be defined as "an attempt to map out and explain fully the richness and complexity of human behavior by studying it from more than one standpoint" (Cohen and Manion 1986).

In this final project, to collect different data sources, the author will conduct interviews with different age groups and genders to avoid group bias.

C. Research Design

This final project is already begun with an interview with the general manager to explore the business issue. The result of the interview with the literature background formed research questions and research objectives. From there the author designed a customer satisfaction semi-structured interview question. After that, the author conducted the interviews. From there, the author analyzed the result using narrative analysis and triangulation method. It then resulted in customer satisfaction and Servicescape if impacted the Number of Players in Klub Golf Bogor Raya. This process is pictured in the figure below:

Research Design

FINDINGS: BUSINESS SOLUTION

A. Narrative Analysis

Using transcripts as what elaborated in the appendix... the narrative analysis conducted is based on the Servicescape perspective. There are ambiance, space/function, and style and decoration. In addition, since the interview is semi-structural and open-ended, the author also included general and additional insights perspective.

The author interviewed respondents with their profiles as showed below:

Name	Age (years old)	Sex	SES	Domicile	Experience in KGBR	Frequency of Games
Eko	46 (Gen X)	Male	A	Bogor	20 years	2-4 times a month
Endang	50 (Gen X)	Male	A	Bogor	±20 years	1-2 times a month
Paryono	48 (Gen X)	Male	A	Tangerang Selatan	±15 years	2 times a month
Rubi	33 (Millennials)	Female	A	Bogor	±17 years	1 time a month
Ira	28 (Millennials)	Female	A	Bogor	3 years	1 time a month
Vincent	23 (Gen Z)	Male	A	Bogor	4 years	1-2 times a month
Farah	31 (Millennials)	Female	A	Jakarta	4 years	2 times a month
Tania	22	Female	A	Bogor	2 years	1 time a month
Abiyoso	33 (Millennials)	Male	A	Bogor	±15 years	3-4 times a month

Respondents' Demographics

As for the SES (Socio-Economic Status), which is a way to group individuals or families based on their economic ability and social status.

Narrative Analysis Based on The Interviews:

No respondents have issue about the temperature in Klub Golf Bogor Raya. Eko's testimony represents the majority of opinions of the respondents, as he said:

“When I was playing in Bogor Raya, I didn't feel that the temperature is too hot or too cold. It was the best when it comes to temperature.” – Eko.

Although, some of them think that it is a bit hot around in the day, but since it is expected, none sees it as a problem:

“I feel like, in Bogor Raya, it is up to when we play. If it is in the morning, it’s chilly. Around 11 am to 12 pm, it is hot. But it is not a problem, since it is expected. It’s similar wherever in any golf field in Bogor.” – Rubi.

In addition to that, the respondents also have a positive perception about the air quality. Bogor is quiet a comfortable place to play if we consider the air.

“The air in Bogor is fresh, I’ve always love playing here. I never found a place as fresh in other places in Java, especially West Java (when it comes to golf fields), or even worse, Jakarta. Therefore it is so much better here in Bogor.” – Endang.

Some of them also mentioned pollution, and in the area, the pollution is not bad since Bogor Raya is in the uptown area.

“It’s fresh, since it is not in a downtown area. And the pollution is not so bad.” – Vincent.

It is not like there is totally absence of noise. The noise that is regularly happening only comes from hole 17 area, since it is close to the toll road, but no one address it as an issue.

“I think the noise in the green area in Bogor Raya is not much. But sometimes in hole 17 it is a bit noisy from the close toll road. But it is not an issue for me.” – Eko.

The rest of the noise, which is a slightly bigger issue, came only occasionally, for example, from maintenance machines.

“I’ve only been disturbed at hole 12, since there is a machine, I think it was a tractor, and the noise is quite loud. However it was one time, so I don’t think that’s an issue worth to address.” – Rubi.

Ira also mentioned, caddies’ noise, which is also not an issue.

“It is in an upperclass neighborhood, therefore it is expected, and is not noisy at all. So I don’t recognize any noise, other than caddies talking, not that it is an issue.” – Ira.

The respondents don’t necessarily have a serious problem so far, including when it comes to smell, Paryono’s response represent the average answers of the respondents:

“I only smell grass and humid air, and it smells nice.” – Paryono.

However, Rubi brought up an issue around Gazebo 9. Players use the area, and it is apparently close to the trash cans.

“Around gazebo 9, I smelled trash a bit once. Probably because it is close to trash cans. Other than that, I don’t have issues.” – Rubi.

Most respondents love the layout of the Green area. However, some perceive the layout more challenging, Paryono’s response for example and Rubi especially:

“The holes look easy. But still some parts are more challenging.” – Paryono.

“Bogor Raya’s green area is difficult and we can hardly see where the turns are, where the breaks are, and how hard should we serve.” – Rubi.

Some just point out it is enjoyable:

“The holes placement are well, the layout is enjoyable.” – Abiyoso.

So far, there is no crucial issue being brought up by the respondents, except the terrain. While the design perceived well, for example according to Eko’s testimony:

“The green area looks mostly flat and easy, but if we are actually standing there, wow, it was amazingly challenging.” – Eko.
The density is too high, according to Endang’s response:

“The experiences are joyous, but the green is a bit too dense.” – Endang.

Also, a few pointed out damages on the terrain, for example, Rubi:

“There are a few noticeable damages on the terrain, I can see.” – Rubi.

As for the style and decoration, respondents have various positive opinions:

“I like the colorful garden, the flower arrangements are beautiful. It sets my mood better.” – Endang.

“Unique, elegant, luxury, the style and decoration never disappoint me.” – Ira.

Abiyoso has a different angle, he pointed out the Balinese style and cultural side:

“The clubhouse is in a Balinese style. It looks original as a golf area. It looks modern but also cultural.” – Abiyoso.

As Jobst (2015) mentioned, servicescape has impacts to customer satisfaction. So far, players’ issues come from the terrain of the Green area and the odor around Gazebo 9. It impacts negatively on their satisfaction.

B. Data Triangulation/Interview Triangulation

Triangulation has its origins in attempts to validate research findings by generating and comparing different sorts of data, and different respondents’ perspectives, on the topic under investigation. In this final project, the data was generated and compared (Carter et.al, 2014).

Interviews are a popular data collection method used in qualitative research. Researchers may use different types of interviews, such as structured, semi-structured, or unstructured interviews, to gather data from participants. Triangulating interviews involves conducting multiple interviews with different participants or conducting interviews with the same participants at different times to validate or corroborate the findings (Torrance, 2012).

The author conducted multiple interviews to different participants to gain richer perspectives. The respondents are gender diverse (four women and five men). They are also diverse in generation. Four of them are boomers, three are millennials, and two are Generation Z. They also have diverged levels of knowledge and expectation. Respondents who identified the issues are the ones who have more knowledge and experience.

In addition to that, the author also triangulate the analysis with recent customer satisfaction survey from Klub Golf Bogor Raya (2023), which is conducted in November 2023 as elaborated below:

Customer Satisfaction Survey, January-June 2023 (Klub Golf Bogor Raya, 2023)

The Green is lower when it comes to satisfaction, compared to the clubhouse and service & food. Respondents in the interview addressed Servicescape issues in the green area, as the lack of satisfaction and the level of dissatisfaction are mainly about the terrain or the physics of the green field, rather than ambiance or style or décor.

In addition to that, the author also triangulated the data with experts’ interviews results. The interviews conversed about Servicescape and are analyzed with narrative analysis as well. The author decided to interview two experts, to cover the business area and gameplay area, both conversing about Servicescape. The first one is a pro-golfer, Benita Yuniarto Kasiadi:

He especially also pointed out about revitalization, over other issues.

“I think the change and progress are not quite good for the field (terrain), the age of this field, especially the Green area is quite old. It hasn’t been revitalized since 1996. KGBR needs to improve here.” - Benita Yuniarto Kasiadi

Kamal Muttaqin, a superintendent who is also an expert in this area added:

“As the superintendent, I have to assess that Green Bogor Raya is worthy of renovation considering that they are quite old and some fields have indeed experienced a decline after Covid. This problem must be resolved immediately because there are several Green Spots that have less consistent speed which hinders the ball's speed and also the contours are wrong. there has been a lot of change in the density of sand, both drainage and several other aspects that affect customer play. We can compare this with Sentul Highland, where they have carried out renovations on several of their greens, therefore some customers have quite good impressions of the greens that have been renovated. This problem must be immediately found a solution. because Green's age will continue to increase.”

The experts, although didn’t mention odor, they did mention about revitalization of the Green area, answering the terrain issues. Therefore, experts’ testimony added up players’ testimony and is relevant to Jobst (2015) that mentioned that the servicescape impacts customer satisfaction.

C. Solution and Proposed Implementation Plan

From the analysis, the author identified the issues in the Green area, such as the ground’s hardness, and ground damages. Therefore, the author suggested repairment and renovation. The author also designed this plan:

Revitalization Timeline

July-September 2024	October-December 2024	January-March 2025
Construction (3 holes)	Grass cultivation (3 holes)	Grass cultivation (3 holes)
Trashcans rearrangement	Construction (3 holes)	Construction (3 holes)

April-June 2025	July-September 2025	October-December 2025	January-March 2026
Grass cultivation (3 holes)			
Construction (3 holes)	Construction (3 holes)	Construction (3 holes)	

Revitalization Timeline

The area of works are depicted in the figures below:

Green area (circled areas are holes placement) The issued trashcans management are around this area:

Current trashcans placement (red circle), close to holes area (blue circle). Green circle is what author suggested the trashcans placement should be.

D. Justification of Implementation Plan

The golf course maintenance department agreed to review the proposed implementation plan for this final project. It gained attention from the department as a better improvement for the department, however, there are other considerations outside of this final project's scope and limitations such as procurement and finance areas.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Respondents who represent the customers in Klub Golf Bogor Raya overall have a rather positive experience. While there is a minor issue about the odor, which is around the Gazebo 9 area, the bigger issue that is worth looking at is the terrain. The terrain is dense and has some noticeable damage. This is also aligned with the fact that the Klub Golf Bogor Raya has not procure revitalized for 27 years, while experts recommend the management revitalize the field every 20 years.

Therefore Klub Golf Bogor Raya needs to improve around the odor and terrain area. Author listed the necessary improvements:

- Trash cans management for Gazebo 9 area
- Green area revitalization

Klub Golf Bogor Raya should discuss it with sanitation experts or professional and eligible contractors.

B. Recommendation

Trash cans management, especially for Gazebo 9 area and field revitalization should be able to resolve the odor and terrain issues. The author also recommended Servicescape research in other area such as clubhouse, restaurant, and event venues for the future researches, based on Jobst's initial research (2015). In addition, the uthor also recommended this business issue to be researched in quantitative research to enrich the servicescape in golf business insights.

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